

Decentralized Resource Discovery, Prediction, and Composition for Inter-Domain Cloud-Edge Orchestration

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Abstract—The rapid growth of intelligent services across the Cloud-Edge Continuum (CEC) is transforming the way computation and data are managed. As services are increasingly deployed across multiple independently operated domains, new orchestration challenges are emerging, especially in environments where privacy, policy differences, and infrastructure diversity make conventional centralized solutions impractical. These limitations are particularly evident in Inter-DIMO (Distributed Intelligent Management Orchestrator) scenarios, where orchestration must happen across domains that operate with limited mutual visibility and trust. To support intelligent coordination in such settings, several key challenges must be addressed: real-time resource discovery without centralized control, anticipating how resources will behave under changing conditions, and dynamically composing services while respecting domain-specific constraints. Resource profiling and advertising represent crucial first steps, enabling resources to be described and shared in ways that support discovery, prediction, and orchestration. The challenge becomes even greater at the edge, where unpredictability, limited visibility, and restricted resource availability are common. To address these issues, current research is increasingly turning to machine learning. Graph-based learning is being explored to enhance semantic discovery and matching, time-series models help forecast availability under highly dynamic conditions, and reinforcement learning techniques support adaptive, distributed service composition. Building on these approaches, orchestration must integrate resource profiling and advertising to ensure resources are not only found and predicted, but also communicated in a way that enables scalable and decentralized coordination across 6G domains. Lightweight metadata exchange, decentralized coordination protocols, and abstract semantic models are being prioritized to promote scalability and interoperability in diverse, fast-changing environments. The forthcoming research will investigate how privacy-preserving learning, semantic-aware service matching, and runtime adaptability can improve orchestration frameworks. The broader goal is to advance toward autonomous, scalable, and resilient orchestration techniques that can meet the requirements of future federated CEC infrastructures.

Index Terms—Cloud-Edge Continuum, 6G, Inter-DIMO, resource profiling, decentralized orchestration, machine learning

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